

**DEVELOPMENT AND COMPLICATIONS
OF DIABETES IN THE BODY**

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Abstract: This article provides information about diabetes, its causes, and the changes and symptoms that occur in the cardiovascular system due to this disease.

This disease develops gradually and suddenly leads to severe complications. At the beginning, the symptoms such as dry mouth, thirst, and weight loss are not obvious. The patient is more disturbed by weakness, fatigue, and thirst. Despite the high content of glucose in the blood, in type 2 diabetes there is an increase in the amount of acetone cells in the blood and its appearance in the urine is very rare. Such patients can live without taking insulin. they can benefit from diet, exercise, and taking blood sugar-lowering drugs.

Keywords: endocrine diseases, insulin, hyperglycemia, genetic factors, somatostatin, glucose, compensation, subcompensation, decompensation, parches

Diabetes is the most common chronic disease in well-developed countries today. The number of patients with this disease is increasing year by year in all countries of the world. This disease is one of the endocrine diseases and develops as a result of the destruction of beta cells that produce the hormone insulin, as well as as a result of autoimmune damage to the pancreas. Because when beta cells are damaged, insulin is not produced enough. Betta cells are non-regenerative cells. As a result of severe stress, a lot of stress, severe fear, these cells are inhibited and cannot be restored. As a result, the metabolism of carbohydrates is disturbed, the conversion of glycogen into glucose

is accelerated, and the absorption and use of glucose by the tissues is reduced, and it accumulates in the blood, as a result, there is an increase in sugar in the blood, it is excreted in the urine, and the patient becomes very fat. Excess sugar in the blood damages blood vessels and capillaries - that is, their walls become more brittle. As a result, the vision of the eye decreases, the image becomes blurry. It should be said here that the problem can manifest itself in one or both eyes at once. At the same time, if the treatment of diabetes is not carried out, the ability to see may be lost over time. Some diseases, such as rubella, viral hepatitis, mumps, as well as some drugs, nitrosamines, and toxic pesticides, can cause gastritis. leads to the destruction of the gland, if more than 80% of its cells are damaged diabetes develops. As a result, a continuous increase in the amount of glucose in the blood is observed - hyperglycemia. Complications caused by this disease can lead to death, this is called hyperglycemic coma.

Diabetes can be severe, mild or moderate. Also, two main types are distinguished. Type 1 diabetes is insulin-dependent and occurs in young children and people under the age of 35. in this type, the natural production of insulin stops completely, therefore, these patients must be constantly injected with insulin. This type is manifested by the following symptoms: nausea, vomiting, and sudden weight loss, and in children, it is difficult to urinate in the evening. Patients of this type may develop life-threatening symptoms. Therefore, patients need urgent help. Type 2 does not depend on insulin. It mainly occurs in people over forty and fifty years of age. Because of this, tissue sensitivity to insulin is impaired. As a result, it becomes difficult for tissues to absorb glucose, and insulin injection is not required. In this case, metabolic processes are disturbed and immunity decreases. As a result of this long-term process, bone tissue is destroyed, that is, osteoporosis develops. Approximately ninety percent of all patients are affected by the second type of diabetes. Also, symptomatic (secondary) diabetes is caused by other diseases (for example: diseases of the pancreas). It is also caused by long-term use of drugs and genetic pathologies. It also occurs as a result of poor

nutrition in people living in tropical regions. Even pregnant women can develop diabetes. and this is called gestational diabetes.

We diagnose this disease when the blood sugar level exceeds 6.5 mmol/l. Normally, the amount of sugar in the blood is 5.5 mmol/l or 80-120 mg%. In case of diabetes, its amount can be 150-250 mg% or even more. When the amount of sugar in the blood is normal, it is excreted through the kidneys with urine. it is not excreted, that is, there is absolutely no sugar in the urine of a healthy person. If the amount of sugar in the blood exceeds 140-150 mg%, it is possible to detect sugar in the urine. Due to the fact that the carbohydrates in the food eaten are not absorbed into the cells and tissues, they are excreted in the urine, so a person becomes hungry quickly and eats quickly. if the fat reserve under the skin breaks down into fatty substances and turns into glucose, even the protein and fatty substances in the cells and tissues are converted into glucose and passes into the blood and is excreted in the urine. As a result, the patient loses weight and becomes weak. and the ability to work decreases. Depending on the level of glucose in the blood, it is described as follows. Combined diabetes - the patient does not complain about his health, the amount of sugar in the blood on an empty stomach does not exceed 4 mmol/l, and during the day does not exceed 9 mmol/l. Subcompensated diabetes symptoms do not appear, but the level of sugar in the blood is from 8 mmol/l to 11 mmol/l. Decompensated diabetes in which the patient complains of a bad condition, symptoms of the disease are detected, the level of glucose in the blood is higher than 11 mmol/l. It should also be clear to us that the origin of this disease depends on other factors besides the endocrine system. These factors include: overweight, genetic predisposition, because 9% of patients with the disease have relatives with diabetes. , as well as improper nutritional composition, including the lack of fiber in the food and the presence of a large number of carbohydrates, chronic intake of drugs, as well as the presence of diseases of the cardiovascular system.

Major Complications of Diabetes

Microvascular

Eye
High blood glucose and high blood pressure can damage eye blood vessels, causing retinopathy, cataracts and glaucoma

Kidney
High blood pressure damages small blood vessels and excess blood glucose overworks the kidneys, resulting in nephropathy.

Neuropathy
Hyperglycemia damages nerves in the peripheral nervous system. This may result in pain and/or numbness. Feet wounds may go undetected, get infected and lead to gangrene.

Macrovascular

Brain
Increased risk of stroke and cerebrovascular disease, including transient ischemic attack, cognitive impairment, etc.

Heart
High blood pressure and insulin resistance increase risk of coronary heart disease

Extremities
Peripheral vascular disease results from narrowing of blood vessels increasing the risk for reduced or lack of blood flow in legs. Feet wounds are likely to heal slowly contributing to gangrene and other complications.

The above information shows that diabetes is a metabolic syndrome, so to speak, this syndrome can be called a complex disaster, because it consists of four terrible diseases: hypertension, ischemic heart disease, and diabetes in the 2nd stage. and obesity, that is, it becomes very fat, it is called abdominal obesity. Also, the arterial pressure increases and becomes less than 130/85 mercury column. This disease is developing more and more in modern times and it has many bad consequences. Causes Hypodynamia, i.e. lack of movement, is the scourge of modern civilization. We are frankly lazy, spending a lot of time on sofas and car seats, watching TV for hours, sitting at the computer and not looking up. let's play, this is the situation at work. We almost stopped walking, we go to the nearest place by bus or by car. In addition, the number of instant, dry foods is increasing day by day. Doctors often attribute the development of metabolic syndrome to not eating breakfast and walking on an empty stomach. This leads to a decrease in the amount of glucose in the blood, resulting in insulin resistance. Well, since the situation has reached this level, the question arises as to what to do now, whether it is possible to correct the situation. This requires us to the most important thing is to try to treat metabolism without drugs, to refrain from bad habits, to walk more, to eat 5-6 times a day less often, to eat less sweets, pasta, refined rice. ,cookies are very useful. Mineral water is also very useful, but it is necessary to consume it in moderation.

Summary. According to the World Health Organization, 30% of the world's population suffers from obesity. 14.9% of them are men and 16.8% are women. 44% of them are over 50 years old. The state of obesity is increasing by 10% every 10 years. As a result of this, diabetes develops, diabetes is diagnosed in one tenth of the world's population. Type 2 diabetes is a widespread disease. 84 million people have the second category of the disease. 65-70% of children born to both parents with diabetes have diabetes.

causes the development of the disease. 15% of the population of our republic suffers from diabetes, they regularly eat diet food and take drugs that reduce the amount of sugar in the blood. This chronic, long-lasting disease damages important body organs, tissues and blood vessels and shows them its complications. First of all, this is seen in the activity of the nervous system. Feet and hands ache, itch and heat up. The perception of pain decreases, the complications of the disease called polyneuropathy intensify. It disables kidney function, as a result, the kidneys are unable to perform their tasks. Eyesight decreases, as a result of a decrease in the body's immune system, purulent wounds on the skin become serious diseases, and blackheads develop on the legs. It is clear that diabetes is considered dangerous due to its complications.

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